

INVESTIGATION OF THE INFLUENCE OF MECHANICAL PRE-DAMAGE AND DEFORMATION RATE ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CFRP/METAL HYBRID PROFILES

M. Muth^{1,*}, A. Kohlund¹, S. Buch¹, K. A. Weidenmann^{1,2}

¹ Institute for Applied Materials (IAM-WK), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Karlsruhe, Germany

² Institute of Materials Resource Management (MRM), University of Augsburg (UNIA), Augsburg, Germany

* Corresponding author (markus.muth@kit.edu)

Keywords: *Hybrids, Joining, Inserts, Bending, Impact*

ABSTRACT

In the work at hand, a structure made out of steel and carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) is under investigation for its properties in quasi-static and dynamic properties. The use of CFRP/metal hybrids has been rising in the production of lightweight structures in the automotive and aerospace industries, where they are often exposed to several quasi-static and dynamic flexural loads. The structures used are steel profiles bonded to CFRP plates by means of adhesive bonding and embedded inserts with the purpose of surrogating state of the art hybrid CFRP/steel structures. In order to perform several flexural loads on the specimens, flexural tests at several deformation rates are performed. Load bearing capacity and stiffness are seen to increase with increasing deformation rate, leading to a much more brittle behaviour at high deformation rates.

In addition, the influence of mechanical pre-damage by an impact on the residual strength of the structure types is evaluated. It is shown, that the adhesively bonded structure shows visible damage in the form of fibre breaks for high impact loads. The residual strength of the adhesively bonded structures after an impact energy of 16J, 25J and 40J was 29% to 41% lower than that of the non-damaged adhesively bonded structures. The adhesively bonded structures with an applied impact energy of 9J showed no loss of strength compared to the non-damaged adhesively bonded structures. Compared to the structures with inserts, the residual strength of this structure type does not change after the pre-damage by impact. Comparing the weight related values the adhesively bonded structures have the higher flexural strength in the absence of impact stresses.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced plastics (FRP) have had an incredible growth in industrial applications due to their outstanding density specific mechanical properties, flexibility in design capabilities and easy fabrication [1]. A great example of a FRP commonly used due to its characteristics are carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP). CFRPs combine the beneficial characteristic properties of carbon fibres, which give CFRP strength and rigidity and a weaker but ductile polymer matrix [1]. The fibres are stronger and stiffer than the matrix, hence, defining the mechanical characteristics of the composite such as its strength and stiffness in fibre direction. Due to its strength and low weight, CFRP has found many applications in aerospace and automotive industry as well as in lightweight design [1, 2].

In automotive and aeronautical industries, the popularity of the combination of metals and FRP's is rising in the design and production of load bearing structures. This is because cost-effective and lightweight parts with high stiffness and load bearing capacity can be produced [3, 4]. An example, that follows this idea, is the combination of metal and FRP's in form of hybrid laminates. Such FRP/Metal hybrid laminates are characterised by excellent mechanical properties at high damage tolerances [3]. There has already been some research in order to understand the mechanical behaviour of these hybrid laminates under tensile and compressive loads by Osiecki et al., Dinca et al. and Jumaat et al. [4–6]. Previous research focused on flexural loads on CFRP/metal hybrids shows the effects of using CFRP to reinforce steel structures [4, 7, 8]. In [4], CFRP/steel hybrids are tested and the results obtained show a

substantial increase of the recorded Young's modulus and flexural stress in transverse fibre direction of the hybrid laminate compared to CFRP laminates. The research performed by [8] is on hybrid aluminium/ CFRP laminates, where 3-point bending tests are performed at several deformation rates. It was concluded that with increasing strain rate the flexural strength decreases as shown by Rajkumar et al. [8]. Finally, in [7] CFRP/titanium hybrids were investigated. Experimental results showed an increase in the bearing strength of the hybrid joints with titanium reinforcements in comparison to CFRP laminates. Additionally, an increase of the bearing strength of the hybrid joints with rising metal content was observed [7].

CFRP/steel hybrids are used in the automotive industry with the main purpose of absorbing crash loads, in which they are being subjected to loading regimes with significant bending moments. Ullah [9] showed that quasi-static and dynamic loads causes locally high stresses and strains which leads to complex damage modes within the laminate due to its heterogeneity and anisotropy. These complex damage modes are dominated by matrix cracking, fibre-matrix debonding, inter- and intra-ply delaminations, fibre fracture and kinking what has been evaluated by Talreja and Singh [10].

Previous studies on the effect of several deformation rates on steel under flexural loads have focused on understanding the changes in the mechanical properties and failure [12, 13]. In their investigation, Śmiglewicz and Jablonska [13] found an increase in the load bearing capacity and the work needed to deform the specimen when increasing strain rate. The study by Huang et al. [12] showed that strain rate exhibited insignificant effect on fracture strain. Increasing strain rate, decreased the strain at which the specimen fractured. The study also confirmed the strength increase of steel with increasing strain rate [12].

Investigations on the effect of several loading rates on the mechanical behaviour of CFRP have been performed mainly under tensile and compressive loading [14]. While more limited, there has still been some research done under flexural loads by Schmack et al., Sánchez-Sáez et al. and Najafi et al. [14–16]. In the investigation done by [14], the maximum load bearing capacity and the specimen midpoint displacement at failure increased at every testing velocity compared to the values obtained in quasi-static tests. The mechanical behaviour of the CFRP on the tests performed by [15] was different to those of [14, 16]. Mechanical strength and stiffness of the laminate under dynamic conditions was lower than under quasi-static conditions. Failure of the laminates revealed that the main failure mechanism of the specimen under both quasi-static and dynamic loads was caused by tensile stresses on the surface opposite to the impact.

When looking at the influence of pre-damage by impact, for low impact energies, FRPs tend to transverse cracks in the individual fibre plies [17]. Unlike metals, FRPs do not show any deformation on the surface, while damage occurs below the surface [18]. If the impact energy falls below a certain threshold, there are neither matrix cracks nor delaminations in the material [19]. With increasing impact energy, additional delaminations occur along the individual fibre plies, which are largest in the lower plies [17]. In [20] CFRP samples were loaded with several impact energies under pressure. It was shown that the residual strength approaches a constant level with increasing impact energy. A cross-ply laminate had a higher strength compared to a woven and quasi-isotropic laminate, but was most sensitive to impact stresses.

While there is already some research on quasi-static bending loads on CFRP / Steel hybrid structures [11], research on the initiation, progression and interaction of various damage modes in these complex structures subjected to several quasi-static and dynamic bending loads, with and without any induced pre-damage, is required. In the work at hand, the specimens under investigation will be CFRP laminates joined to steel profiles by means of adhesive bonding or embedded inserts. The aim of is to determine the damage in the specimen under several types of stress (quasi-static, dynamic) and investigate the effect of pre-damages applied by impact on the mechanical behaviour of the specimen. To evaluate the effect of deformation rate and impact loads on the mechanical behaviour of the specimens and variations of load bearing capacity between several deformation rates will be investigated and discussed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Material and specimen geometry

The CFRP part of the structures are manufactured by Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) process at Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), institute of production science (wbk). The CFRP samples consist of a series of eight plies of biaxial nonwoven carbon fibre fabric (Hexcel NLT00). The epoxy matrix system by Sika® (Biresin® CR170/CH150-3) is cured for 60 minutes at 70°C and an infiltration pressure of 9 bar. The resulting fibre volume fraction is 44.4%. The dimensions after trimming are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Dimensions (in mm) of the structure with a) the adhesive bonding and b) the inserts.

The hat profile is made from sheet-material which has been formed to the desired shape as shown in Figure 2a). All inserts, dimensions shown in Figure 2b), and also the hat profiles are made of stainless steel (ANSI 304) to prevent corrosion which will be investigated in the future. The inserts are placed during preforming between the upper and lower four plies of fabric.

Figure 2: Dimensions (in mm) of a) the hat profile and b) the inserts used.

Mechanical tests are performed by using two types of structures. The first type is made out of a CFRP plate where a hat profile is post-cured as illustrated in Figure 3a). Therefore the UHU Endfest 300 is used as the adhesive, cured for 60 minutes at 70°C.

The second type of structure consists of the CFRP plate where 14 inserts are integrated as shown in Figure 3b). The hat profile is fastened to the inserts by using screws of strength class 12.9.

Figure 3: Exemplary images of the structures with a) adhesive bonding and b) inserts.

2.2 Experimental setup

The expected loads for the structural parts are crash scenarios. Thus, testing has to deal with the absorption of crash loads and the test setup and specimen geometry differ from geometries used in [21–24] where only punctiform load introduction elements were under investigation. The dimensions of the three-point-bending setup are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Dimensions (in mm) of the three-point-bending setup used.

The quasi-static (0.033 mm/s) and dynamic flexural bending tests with 0.25 mm/s deformation rate were performed on a 100 kN Zwick universal testing machine and the dynamic bending tests (250 mm/s and $15 \cdot 10^3$ mm/s) are performed using the Amsler HTM 5020 by Zwick Roell. The deformation is continuously applied until the maximum deflection of the position transducer is reached. The pre-damage/impact tests were carried out with a drop tower (Instron dynatup type 9250HV) based on DIN EN 6038 [25].

Figure 5 shows the setup of the impact test.

Figure 5: Dimensions (in mm) of the impact setup used.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Pre-damage by impact

First, impact tests at the drop tower are carried out. When looking at the visible damages after impact, the adhesively bonded structures show no visible damage for an impact energy of 9J, whereas for energies of more than 16J the hat profile on one side is detached from the CFRP base plate, as highlighted in. This crack length increases with increasing impact energy.

Figure 6: Rupture of the CFRP/steel interface for an adhesively bonded structure damaged with 40 J.

The structures with inserts have only been pre-damaged with 25J and 40J impact energy due to a missing number of parts. This structure type shows no optical visible damage on the outside of the structure either after the impact tests.

3.2 Quasi-static bending test

Figure 7 shows the results for the two structure types and the several impact energies in the quasi-static (residual strength) tests. The residual strength of the 40J pre-damaged adhesively bonded structures is 41 % less than the residual strength of the non-damaged adhesively bonded structures. Here the residual strength decreases only by 10% for an impact energy of 40J for the structures with inserts.

Figure 7: Residual strength of structures tested depending on the impact energy.

As shown in Figure 6 there are cracks in the interface between the CFRP and the hat profile. The crack length depending on the chosen impact energy is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Crack length in the CFRP/steel interface after the impact tests.

3.3 Dynamic bending tests

In Figure 9 the force versus the crosshead displacement is figured out for the deformation rates tested. The curves for 0.033 mm/s, 0.25 mm/s and 250 mm/s have a similar shape. The curve for $15 \cdot 10^3$ mm/s varies significantly in shape compared to the other velocities, as it oscillates heavily which is due to a resonance in the experimental setup which makes it necessary to perform further investigations for these high deformation rates and these results won't be taken into account in the further course of the work at hand.

Figure 9: Force-displacement exemplary curves for all deformation rates investigated.

The load bearing capacities, which is defined as the maximum force recorded during flexural bending tests, show that the highest increase in load bearing capacity between the deformation rates is seen when increasing the deformation rate from 0.25 mm/s to 250 mm/s, as it increases by 17.2% as illustrated in Figure 10. Because of a lack of structures available of the insert structures no tests between 0.033 mm/s and 15 m/s have been performed.

Figure 10: Load bearing capacity of the structures tested depending on the deformation rate.

Failure modes occurring of the tests with several deformation rates present in the CFRP plate of the adhesively bonded structures shown in Figure 11 are fibre and matrix fracture and slight delamination of the plies. Complete fibre and matrix fracture are only present in the centre section middle section of the laminate. The steel profile has been deformed at the point where the load has been applied. What is immediately apparent is the degree of laminate damage (delamination, fracture of the fibres and the matrix, etc.) with increasing deformation rate, which can be seen when comparing Figure 11a) with Figure 11d).

Figure 11: Damage of the CFRP laminate and steel profile after a 3- point bending test with a crosshead velocity of a) 0.033 mm/s b) 0.25 mm/s c) 250 mm/s d) $15 \cdot 10^3$ mm/s.

In the specimens with embedded inserts tested at 0.033 mm/s the laminate has slightly fractured only at one side of the specimen. Moreover, the steel profile has been flattened throughout most of the area of the profile. For the specimens with inserts tested at $15 \cdot 10^3$ mm/s the laminate is again strongly deformed, as highlighted in Figure 12. However, there is also delamination of the plies in the laminate. The steel profile has a significant amount of plastic deformation, but of a less degree than the steel profile deformed at 0.033 mm/s. There is buckling of the profile between the inserts as well as flattening of the profile in the area where the load has been applied for both deformation rates.

Figure 12: Damage of specimens with inserts at a) 0.033 mm/s and b) $15 \cdot 10^3$ mm/s.

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 Influence of pre-damage by impact

It was shown that from an impact energy of 16J upwards a different damage behaviour during the quasi-static bending test was observed for the adhesively bonded structures. Also it is shown in Figure 7 that the variance in the load bearing capacity is the highest for an impact load of 16J. This leads to the conclusion that the critical impact load for this structure is in the region of 16J. This is due to the increasing amount of damage in the laminate and the interface caused by the impact. The failure of the adhesive joint was initiated at the level of the outermost ends of the hat profile, since this is where the highest peel and shear stresses act (c.f. [26]). It should be noted that the length of the detached adhesive bond for the bonded structures varied after the impact tests. The higher the impact energy, the longer the detached bond was (c.f. Figure 8). The lack of adhesion due to the detached steel profile, on one side is the reason for the lower loads transferred via the interface into the laminate compared to non-pre-damaged structures. The critical impact energy mentioned, which is 16J for the adhesive bonded structures is for the insert structures presumably above 40J which represents the highest impact energy tested and needs to be investigated in the future.

For the non-damaged structures, it can be seen that the adhesively bonded structures have a bending strength 22 % higher than the structures with inserts shown in Figure 7. This difference is even higher than the difference of 12 % found in [11], which is probably due to the different size of the CFRP base plate of $194 \times 275 \text{ mm}^2$ (in the work at hand: $150 \times 270 \text{ mm}^2$). The higher strength of the adhesively bonded structure is due to the fact that the hat profile can transfer the load to a larger area than the structures with inserts, as explained by the authors [11]. Due to the more local load introduction of the inserts, stress peaks arose, especially at the insert edge. The effect of the impact on the adhesively bonded structures have a higher influence on the residual load bearing capacity than on the structures with inserts. These effects can be attributed to the different damage behaviour during the impact test. The flexural load bearing capacity of the adhesively bonded structures is 25 % lower than that of structures with inserts after an impact with 40J.

Since composites with CFRP are used because of their high weight-specific strength compared to metals, it is important to consider the weight of the structures. In this case, the inserts lead to an increase in the structure's weight. The adhesively bonded structures are 37 % (350 g vs. 555 g) lighter than structures with inserts. Regarding the weight, the structures with inserts have a 15 % lower weight-specific bending strength after an impact energy of 25 J than the adhesively bonded structures which is presented in Figure 13.

Regarding the weight, the adhesively bonded structure is therefore superior to the structure with inserts in terms of the achieved bending strength values, the non-damaged and the pre-damaged structures. Nevertheless, it must be noted that the structures with inserts showed no visible damage after

the applied impact energies, while the adhesively bonded structures were detached on one side. Thus the adhesively bonded, pre-damaged structure is more sensitive to impact loads, a workaround to use the beneficial features of both structure types it should be the goal to integrate the hat profile into the laminate without using any additional load transferring element.

Figure 13: Weight-specific residual strength of the structures.

4.2 Influence of the deformation rate

Additionally, the curves in the force-displacement graph have steeper slopes in the elastic region and higher yield strengths than the classical force-displacement curves for metals. The reason for the different stiffness is the stiffness of the CFRP laminate which is also a part of the structure presented.

Altogether, it can be concluded that load bearing capacity increases with increasing deformation rate, based on the increase of average maximum force seen with increasing deformation rate at 0.25 mm/s and 0.25 m/s. Load bearing capacity increases by a maximum of 18.1 % when increasing the deformation rate from quasi-static to dynamic deformation rates. This is slightly lower than the minimum 20 % increase of load bearing capacity of the specimen obtained by Schmack [14], when comparing the maximum force recorded in dynamic tests (0.5 m/s; 5 m/s; 10 m/s) and quasi-static tests. This discrepancy can be deduced to the fact that the tested specimens by [14] are CFRP laminates without any connected steel element, while the specimens tested in the work at hand were hybrid CFRP/steel structures. In the specimens used and investigated, both the properties of steel and CFRP will influence the mechanical behaviour of the specimen.

Although it can be assumed that the load bearing capacity of the structures with inserts will also increase at higher deformation rates, a statement on this is not possible with the selected parameters due to the curve shape of the force-displacement curves for high deformation rates. A comparison for deformation rates between 0.033 mm/s and $15 \cdot 10^3$ mm/s is not possible yet because of a lack of number of structures of this type. The reason for the higher load bearing capacity for quasi-static loads is, as already discussed by the authors [11], since the adhesively bonded hat profile has a much larger load transferring area than the specimens with inserts have.

In contrast to the results of [14], the failure of the CFRP laminate, as can also be seen in the investigations of [11] always occurred due to tensile stresses on the side of the laminate opposing to the load introduction. However, this is probably due to the fact that the load is not introduced directly into the laminate but is redirected from the steel profile into the laminate. Contrary to the investigation done by [14], where load is directly applied onto the CFRP laminate. The damage modes observed on all the

CFRP laminates were matrix and fibre fracture and delamination in the region of the laminate where the highest strains occur. At higher deformation rates the degree of fibre and matrix fracture and delamination was higher. At 250 mm/s and $15 \cdot 10^3$ mm/s the CFRP laminate had completely fractured into two sections. Based on the values for strain change from the strain gauges at higher deformation rates the specimen behaved in a more brittle manner. Finally, the steel profile only deformed plastically at the point where the load was applied this was the case at all deformation rates. For specimens with embedded inserts the only failure modes present were a small crack on the specimen tested at 0.033 mm/s and delamination of the plies at the specimen tested at $15 \cdot 10^3$ mm/s. Additionally, the steel profile at both deformation rates showed buckling between the insert studs and flattening of the hat profile. The degree of hat profile flattening was higher at 0.033 mm/s.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The aim of the work at hand was to evaluate the deformation rate effect and influence of mechanical pre-damage by impact on the mechanical behaviour and failure of the presented structure types. The comparison between the adhesively bonded structures and the structures with inserts shows, that the bending strength of the adhesively bonded, non-damaged structures is higher than the structures with inserts. The structures with inserts have a higher residual strength than the adhesively bonded structures, but are also characterised by a higher weight. With the calculation of the weight, the adhesively bonded structures have a higher weight-specific residual strength. Nevertheless, it should be considered that the impact sensitivity of the insert structure was much lower than that of the adhesively bonded structures. Also the insert structure showed no visible damage, which should be particularly relevant for safety applications. and will be taken into account for the design of the next structure type to be investigated. Finally, it should be noted that the damage behaviour of the adhesively bonded structures differs from that of the structures with inserts. The adhesively bonded structure is superior to the structures with inserts in the case of pure bending stress. At a critical impact energy of 16 J and higher, however, it has decisive disadvantages regarding the residual load bearing capacity compared to structures with inserts.

Regarding the influence of deformation rate, an increase in strength and load bearing capacity of the adhesive bonded structures was observed with increasing deformation rate. Failure modes are strain dependent and different final failure profiles are seen at several deformation rates, however the initiation and propagation of cracks at the CFRP surface in adhesively bonded specimens is identical for all deformation rates. The main failure mechanisms present in adhesively bonded specimens were fibre and matrix fracture and delamination. In specimens with inserts, there was no fracture of the laminate, just small cracks were present in addition to delamination of the plies.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) SPP1712 „Intrinsic hybrid composites for lightweight load-bearings“, project WE 4273/11-2 “Fundamental research of intrinsically produced FRP-/metal-composites – from embedded insert to load bearing hybrid structure” (Karlsruhe Institute of Technology). The authors would like to thank the institute of production science (wbk) of KIT for the manufacturing of the specimens and structures.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bunsell, A. R., Renard J.: *Fundamentals of fibre reinforced composite materials*, CRC Press, 2005.
- [2] Gay, D.: *Composite materials: Design and applications*, CRC Press, 2014.
- [3] Seidlitz, H., Gerstenberger, C., Osiecki, T., Simon, S., Kroll, L.: *High-performance lightweight structures with fiber reinforced thermoplastics and structured metal thin sheets*. Journal of Materials Science Research, 4(1):28, 2015.
- [4] Osiecki, T., Gerstenberger, C., Hackert, A., Seidlitz, H., Kroll, L.: *Thermoplastic fiber reinforced/metal-hybrid laminates for structural lightweight applications*. In: Proc. 23rd Annual International Conference on Composites/Nano Engineering (ICCE-23), 2015.

- [5] Dinca, I., Ștefan, A., Stan, A.: *Aluminum/glass fibre and aluminum/carbon fibre hybrid laminates*. Incas Bull, 2 2066 – 2081, 2010.
- [6] Jumaat, F. A., Sivakumar, D.: *Investigation on the mechanical properties of hybrid fibre material laminate*. Proceedings of Mechanical Engineering Research Day 2017, 2017 314 – 315, 2017.
- [7] Cardoso, C. M. T.: *Hybrid CFRP/Titanium bolted joints*, 2017.
- [8] Rajkumar, G. R., Krishna, M., Narasimhamurthy, H. N., Keshavamurthy, Y. C., Nataraj, JR: *Investigation of tensile and bending behavior of aluminum based hybrid fiber metal laminates*. Procedia Materials Science, 5 60 – 68, 2014.
- [9] Ullah, H.: *Analysis of mechanical behaviour and damage of carbon fabric-reinforced composites in bending*, Loughborough, 2013.
- [10] Talreja R., Singh C. V.: *Damage and failure of composite materials*, Cambridge University Press, 2012.
- [11] Muth, M., Weidenmann, K. A.: *Three-Point Bending Test on CFRP-Steel Profile Hybrid Structures*. In: Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Hybrid Materials and Structures, 2018.
- [12] Huang, G., Yan, B., Zhu, H.: *The effect of strain rate on tensile properties and fracture strain*. In: Presentation at great Design in Steel Seminar, 2011.
- [13] Jabłońska, M. B., Śmiglewicz, A., Niewielski, G.: *The effect of strain rate on the mechanical properties and microstructure of the high-Mn steel after dynamic deformation tests*. Archives of Metallurgy and Materials, 60(2):577 – 580, 2015.
- [14] Schmack, T., Righi, R., Huelsbusch, D., Rausch, J., Roquette, D., Deinzer, G., Kothmann, M., Kassapoglou, C., Walther, F.: *A newly-developed fixture and testing method for strain rate-dependent flexural properties determination of carbon/epoxy composites*, 2017.
- [15] Sánchez-Sáez, S., Barbero, E., Navarro, C.: *Analysis of the dynamic flexural behaviour of composite beams at low temperature*. Composites science and technology, 67(11-12):2616 – 2632, 2007.
- [16] Najafi, M., Khalili, S. M. R., Eslami-Farsani, R.: *The Strain Rate Effect on Bending Properties of Basalt and Carbon Fibers Reinforced Phenolic Composites*. International Journal of Advanced Design and Manufacturing Technology, 5(4):33, 2012.
- [17] Wu, G., Wang, H.-T., Wu, Z.-S., Liu, H.-Y., Ren, Y.: *Experimental study on the fatigue behavior of steel beams strengthened with different fiber-reinforced composite plates*. Journal of Composites for Construction, 16(2):127 – 137, 2011.
- [18] Richardson, M. O.W., Wisheart, M. J.: *Review of low-velocity impact properties of composite materials*. Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, 27(12):1123 – 1131, 1996.
- [19] Davila, C. G., Pinho, S. T., Remmers, J. J.C.: *Mechanical Response of Composites. Computational Methods in Applied Sciences*, Springer, 2008.
- [20] Wang, S.-X., Wu, L.-Z., Ma, L.: *Low-velocity impact and residual tensile strength analysis to carbon fiber composite laminates*. Materials & Design, 31(1):118 – 125, 2010.
- [21] Fleischer, J., Gebhardt, J.: *Experimental investigation of metal inserts embedded in composite parts manufactured by the RTM process*. In: 13th Japan International SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition, Nagoya, Japan, 2013.
- [22] Pottmeyer, F., Muth, M., Weidenmann, K. A.: *Research of the Load Bearing Capacity of Shape-Optimized Metal Inserts Embedded in CFRP under Different Types of Stresses*. In: Key Engineering Materials, Vol. 742, 2017.
- [23] Gebhardt, J., Pottmeyer, F., Fleischer, J., Weidenmann, K.: *Characterization of metal inserts embedded in carbon fiber reinforced plastics*. In: Materials Science Forum, 2015.
- [24] Gebhardt, J., Fleischer, J.: *Experimental investigation and performance enhancement of inserts in composite parts*. Procedia CIRP, 23 7 – 12, 2014.
- [25] DIN German Institute for Standardization: *Luft- und Raumfahrt - Faserverstärkte Kunststoffe - Prüfverfahren - Bestimmung der Restdruckfestigkeit nach Schlagbeanspruchung*, Beuth Verlag GmbH, Berlin 201649.025.40 (DIN EN 6038).
- [26] Vaidya, U. K., Gautam, A. R. S., Hosur, M., Dutta, P.: *Experimental-numerical studies of transverse impact response of adhesively bonded lap joints in composite structures*. International journal of adhesion and adhesives, 26(3):184 – 198, 2006.